

[original insight]

Diamond Open Access

[awaiting peer review]

Negative mass as a source of gravity

Open Quantum Collaboration*

February 13, 2024

Abstract

We propose that negative mass can be the source of gravity in the quantum vacuum.

keywords: negative mass, curvature, vacuum, quantum gravity

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/k4gtz/download>
<https://zenodo.org/record/10655570>

Source of negative curvature

1. Positive mass/energy curves spacetime [1].
2. Negative mass/energy curves spacetime.
3. Curvature is due to sources of gravity (matter/energy).
4. Suppose the vacuum state of our universe is described by Anti-de Sitter space (AdS) [2].
5. AdS has negative curvature.

*All *authors* with their *affiliations* appear at the end of this white paper.

6. So, according to (4) and (5), our spacetime has negative curvature.
7. If the curvature is negative, then a source of negative mass/energy is fulfilling our universe.
8. The source (7) is provided by quantum mechanics, that is, the quantum properties of spacetime (vacuum).

Mass entanglement

9. Conjecture: positive mass is entangled with negative mass.
10. Let
 - (a) $|q\rangle$ = quantum vacuum state
 - (b) $|+\rangle / |-\rangle$ = state of positive/negative energy
 - (c) m_+/m_- = amplitude of positive/negative mass
11. $|q\rangle = m_+ |+-\rangle + m_- |-+\rangle$
12. Breaking the entanglement (11) leads to free negative energy [3].

Final Remarks

13. Classical vacuum states might be the result of quantum phenomena, such as: spacetime pouring [3], Hawking radiation applied to ordinary matter [4], dark matter [5], and other effects [6].

Open Invitation

*Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [7, 8].
Join the **Open Quantum Collaboration**.*

Supplementary files

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [9].

How to cite this paper?

<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/k4gtz>

<https://zenodo.org/record/10655570>

Acknowledgements

+ **Center for Open Science**

<https://cos.io>

+ **Open Science Framework**

<https://osf.io>

+ **Zenodo**

<https://zenodo.org>

Agreement

All authors agree with [8].

License

CC-By Attribution 4.0 International [11]

References

- [1] Misner, Charles W., Kip S. Thorne, and John Archibald Wheeler. *Gravitation*. Princeton University Press, 2017.

- [2] Witten, Edward. “Anti de Sitter space and holography.” *arXiv preprint hep-th/9802150* (1998). <https://arxiv.org/pdf/hep-th/9802150.pdf>
- [3] Lobo, Matheus P. “Spacetime Pouring.” *OSF Preprints*, 21 May 2019. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/zwfb5>
- [4] Lobo, Matheus P. “Ordinary Matter and Dark Energy.” *OSF Preprints*, 25 May 2019. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ersvu>
- [5] Lobo, Matheus P. “Dark Matter and Bubbles of Void.” *OSF Preprints*, 11 July 2019. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/w7m3q>
- [6] Lobo, Matheus P. “Gravity Extracts Virtual Particles from the Quantum Vacuum (Davies-Fulling-Unruh Effect).” *OSF Preprints*, 19 May 2019. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/tq7m2>
- [7] Lobo, Matheus P. “Microarticles.” *OSF Preprints*, 28 Oct. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/ejrct>
- [8] Lobo, Matheus P. “Simple Guidelines for Authors: Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics.” *OSF Preprints*, 15 Nov. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/fk836>
- [9] Lobo, Matheus P. “Open Journal of Mathematics and Physics (OJMP).” *OSF*, 21 Apr. 2020. <https://osf.io/6hzyf/files>
- [10] <https://zenodo.org/record/10655570>
- [11] CC. Creative Commons. *CC-By Attribution 4.0 International*. <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>

The Open Quantum Collaboration

Matheus Pereira Lobo (lead author, mplobo@uft.edu.br)¹

David Adjei²

¹Federal University of Tocantins (Brazil)

²Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (Ghana)